

BEHAVIOUR OF FIBRE REINFORCED CONCRETE BEAMS UNDER IMPACT LOADING

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Impact tests were carried out on plain and fibre reinforced concrete beams, using a drop weight instrumented impact machine. The beams, 125mm wide, 150mm deep, and 1400mm long, were struck at midspan by a hammer weighing 3385N, and falling through 0.5m. Both normal strength and high strength concretes were tested. Two types of fibres, steel and polypropylene, were used. It was found that both plain and fibre reinforced concrete are strain rate sensitive materials. Fibre reinforced concrete, under impact loading, was found to have improved strength and ductility compared to plain concrete.

INTRODUCTION

Concrete is a brittle, strain rate sensitive material (1-2). With its heterogeneous structure, it is found to behave differently when subjected to high strain rate loading, as compared to its behaviour under quasi-static loading. At present, the behaviour of concrete under variable stress rates can be predicted only on the basis of empirical equations (2) derived from fracture mechanics models. However, since no general agreement exists regarding the validity of the application of fracture mechanics to concrete, such predictions of strain rate effects on concrete are of limited usefulness.

Currently, there is a great deal of interest in achieving higher strengths in concrete. However, high strength concrete has also been found to be more brittle than normal strength concrete (3). This limits the use of high strength concrete in the situations where the possibility of impact or shock loading exists, though concrete structures may well be subjected to occasional shocks or impact loading. Because of the complex stress wave patterns, and the complex energy transfer and dissipation mechanisms associated with impact, it is not realistic to assume that impact is simply an extreme case of high strain rate loading. Impact loading is generally associated with a large amount of external energy suddenly imparted to the structure. To be able to use concrete under impact loading, the addition of fibres has been suggested, since the post-elastic ductility observed in the case of fibre reinforced concretes, also predicts a greatly enhanced impact resistance of these composites over that of plain unreinforced concrete (4,5). An assessment of the impact resistance, however, can not be made on the basis of conventional static tests; proper impact tests must be carried out. Unfortunately, there are at present no standard testing techniques for impact. In this study, the effect of fibres on the performance of both normal and high

strength concrete under impact loading has been studied, using an instrumented drop weight impact machine.

EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURES

The instrumented drop weight impact machine (Fig. 1) used in this study has been described in full elsewhere (6). Basically, the machine is capable of dropping a 345 kg mass hammer from heights of up to 2.3m. Strain gauges mounted in the striking end of the hammer (called the 'tup') are used to record the contact load between the impacting hammer and the beam. Additional strain gauges are also mounted in one of the support anvils, to monitor the reactions. Three accelerometers are placed along the length of the beam to monitor the response of the beam itself. A 5-channel data acquisition system based upon an IBM PC, is used to collect the data; the five channels can be read simultaneously at 200 microsecond intervals. The data thus acquired are stored on a magnetic disc; they are then transferred to a main frame computer for analysis.

Fig. 1. The instrumented impact machine. The machine stands about 4.5m above the floor.

SPECIMENS

The details of the production of the concrete beams with the dimensions (length \times width \times depth) of 1400mm \times 100mm \times 125mm have been given elsewhere (6). The normal strength concrete beams, made with CSA Type 10 normal portland cement (equivalent to ASTM Type I), with a maximum aggregate size of 10mm, had the following mix proportions:

water:cement:fine aggregate:coarse aggregate = 0.5:1.0:2.0:3.5

This concrete had developed an average strength of about 42 MPa at the time of testing. High strength concrete was made in the same way as normal strength concrete, but in addition, 16% condensed silica fume¹ (by weight of cement) was added to the mix. The mix proportions were then:

water:cement:microsilica:fine aggregate:coarse aggregate
= 0.33:0.86:0.14:1.57:1.04

This resulted in a concrete with a compressive strength of about 82 MPa at the time of testing. The steel fibre reinforced concrete contained, in addition, 1.5% by volume of steel fibres. These fibres were 50mm long and 0.60mm in diameter, with both ends hooked². Polypropylene fibre reinforced concrete contained 0.5% by volume of 37mm long fibrillated polypropylene fibres³. All of the beams were stored in a moist room until they were tested, at test ages varying from 3-6 months.

METHOD OF TESTING AND ANALYSIS OF RESULTS

The concrete beams were tested as described in (6). Briefly, the testing involved mounting the accelerometers on the beam, supporting the beam on the test anvils, raising the hammer to the required height, and finally, letting it drop on the beam. With the data acquisition system triggered by a photocell attached to the hammer, the strain gauges and the accelerometers were read simultaneously at 200 microsecond intervals.

The use of three accelerometers on the beam itself (Fig. 2a) provided the acceleration distribution along the length of the beam. This, in turn, could be used to generate the shape of the deformed beam undergoing impact. Results from these tests, and from many other tests not reported here, supported the assumption made in (6) that the accelerations and displacements along the length of the beam (Fig. 2b), were linearly distributed.

The Generalized Inertial Load

Knowing the accelerations along the length of the beam, the distributed inertial forces can be replaced by a generalized inertial load $P_i(t)$ acting at the centre (6).

$$P_i(t) = \rho A \ddot{u}_0(t) \left[\frac{l}{3} + \frac{8}{3} \frac{h^3}{l^2} \right] \quad (1)$$

where

- $P_i(t)$ = generalized inertial load
- ρ = mass density of concrete
- A = area of cross-section of the beam
- $\ddot{u}_0(t)$ = acceleration at the centre
- l = span of the test beam
- h = length of the overhang

¹EMSAC, produced by Elkem Chemicals, Inc., Pittsburgh, Pennsylvania.

²Produced by Bekaert N.V., Belgium.

³Produced by Forta Corporation, Grove City, Pennsylvania.

Fig. 2. Calculation of the generalized inertial load.

The Generalized Bending Load

Once the generalized inertial load $P_i(t)$ at the centre is known, the beam can be modelled as a Single Degree of Freedom System (SDOF), and the actual bending load (the spring force) can be evaluated using the equation of dynamic equilibrium,

$$P_b(t) = P_t(t) - P_i(t) \quad (2)$$

where

- $P_b(t)$ = generalized bending load
- $P_t(t)$ = observed tup load
- $P_i(t)$ = generalized inertial load

The Deflections and Velocities at the Centre

Velocities ($u_0(t)$) and deflections ($u_0(t)$) at the centre of the beam were calculated by integration of the midspan acceleration with respect to time:

$$\dot{u}_0(t) = \int_0^t \ddot{u}_0(t) dt \quad (3)$$

$$u_0(t) = \int_0^t \dot{u}_0(t) dt \quad (4)$$

The Beam Energy

The energy consumed by the beam in the process of deforming is then equal to the area under the bending load ($P_b(t)$) vs. central deflection ($u_0(t)$) plot (6).

RESULTS

Tables 1 and 2 present the behaviour of normal strength (NS) concrete and high strength (HS) concrete, respectively. Table 3 presents the

Table 1
Normal Strength Concrete

	Plain Concrete		Plain + PP Fibres		Plain + Steel Fibres	
	Static (3)*	Impact (7)*	Static (3)*	Impact (6)*	Static (3)*	Impact (6)*
Max. Observed Tip Load (n)	-	36192 (677)	-	38318 (1584)	-	39999 (2345)
Max. Inertial Load (N)	-	18244 (1278)	-	21018 (1267)	-	15993 (1262)
Peak Bending Load (N)	6344 (306)	16932 (428)	7302 (99)	17300 (821)	11500 (670)	24006 (1629)
Fracture Energy (Nm)	5.5 (1.5)	90.1 (6.5)	14.0 (4.5)	119.4 (8.1)	44.8 (2.0)	237.6 (7.5)
Speed of Cross Head or Drop Hammer (m/s)	4×10^{-7}	3.1	4×10^{-7}	3.1	4×10^{-7}	3.1

Note: Numbers in parentheses are the standard deviations.
*Number of specimens tested.

Table 2
High Strength Concrete

	Plain Concrete		Plain + PP Fibres		Plain + Steel Fibres	
	Static (3)*	Impact (7)*	Static (3)*	Impact (6)*	Static (3)*	Impact (6)*
Max. Observed Tip Load (n)	-	36652 (1725)	-	37207 (1109)	-	46612 (1244)
Max. Inertial Load (N)	-	17892 (1132)	-	19063 (1189)	-	19011 (1244)
Peak Bending Load (N)	9720 (1809)	18760 (446)	13206 (787)	18144 (549)	17996 (1316)	27601 (1646)
Fracture Energy (Nm)	2.8 (0.5)	74.9 (18.6)	8.7 (2.9)	92.2 (7.4)	61.4 (5.5)	252.6 (14.6)
Speed of Cross Head or Drop Hammer (m/s)	4×10^{-7}	3.1	4×10^{-7}	3.1	4×10^{-7}	3.1

Note: Numbers in parentheses are the standard deviations.
*Number of specimens tested.

ratios of the values obtained in impact to those obtained from static tests. Table 4 presents the comparison between the two fibres. Figure 3 shows the load vs. displacement plots obtained using conventional static rates of loading for both plain and fibre reinforced NS concrete. It can be seen that the addition of both types of fibres enhances the deformation capacity of NS concrete. The high modulus steel fibres are more effective than the low modulus polypropylene fibres, in that both the peak bending loads and the fracture energies were higher in the case of steel fibre reinforced concrete. Figure 4 shows the load vs. displacement plots for plain and fibre reinforced NS concretes under impact. Again, the effects of fibre reinforcement, particularly steel fibres, can be seen in the form of improved strength and ductility.

Table 3
Strain Rate Effects - Ratios Between Values
in Impact/Values in Static Loading

	NS	NS + PP	NS + STEEL	HS	HS + PP	HS + STEEL
Bending Load	2.67	2.37	2.08	1.93	1.37	1.53
Energy	17.4	8.52	5.4	26.8	10.6	4.11

Table 4
Effect of Fibres on Increase in Properties in Static in Dynamic Tests
(Values of Specimens with Fibres Relative
to the Same Matrix Without Fibres)

		Ratios of Bending Loads		Ratios of Energies	
		Static	Impact	Static	Impact
NS	PP Fibres	1.15	1.02	2.54	1.33
	Steel Fibres	1.81	1.42	8.14	2.63
HS	PP Fibres	1.36	0.97	3.10	1.23
	Steel Fibres	1.85	1.47	21.9	3.37

Figures 5 and 6 show the static and impact performance, respectively, of plain and fibre reinforced HS concrete. As in the case of NS concrete, fibre inclusions were found to improve the strength and the fracture energy of HS concrete.

DISCUSSION

The addition of fibres can be used to modify the brittle type of failure observed for unreinforced cement-based matrices under impact loading. The effects of fibres can be seen particularly in the improved

Fig. 3. Static behaviour of plain and fibre reinforced normal strength concrete

Fig. 4. Dynamic behaviour of plain and fibre reinforced normal strength concrete.

flexural strength of the composites, and also in their improved impact resistance, or toughness. It is not so much the improved strength, but rather the improved toughness, which is the prime advantage of adding fibres to the matrix. The fibres form primarily a mechanical bond with the surrounding matrix. A cracked composite carries load by virtue of the tensile strength of the fibre, and the bond that has developed between the fibre and the matrix. When the brittle concrete matrix cracks, the fibres bridging the crack can still transfer some load, and sudden failure is thereby averted. This imparts to the composite some post-cracking ductility which leads to the improved toughness. Once the composite has cracked, however, the matrix-fibre system is no longer a continuous medium, and conventional theories of mechanics may be inapplicable.

Fig. 5. Static behaviour of plain and fibre reinforced high strength concrete.

Fig. 6. Dynamic behaviour of plain and fibre reinforced high strength concrete.

High modulus steel fibres with hooked ends were found to behave better than the low modulus, straight, chopped polypropylene fibres. The steel fibres, which are hooked in order to provide additional mechanical bond, increased the load carrying capacity in the post-cracking region more than did the polypropylene fibres, which appeared to have a lower bond strength with the concrete. In addition, the high tensile strength of steel fibres resulted primarily in a pull-out type of failure, though some breaking of fibres was noted; in the case of the polypropylene fibres, with a much lower tensile strength, only breaking of fibres was observed. An increasing number of steel fibres were found to break with an increase in the applied stress rate (7). An interesting observation in the case of steel fibre reinforced concrete (Figs. 3-6) was the disconti-

nuity observed in their load vs. displacement plots before the absolute peak load was reached. The discontinuity probably corresponded to the matrix failure and subsequent transfer of load from the matrix to the fibres that bridged the crack matrix. The pull-out conditions for these bridging fibres were probably not attained at the point of matrix failure, and thus a further increase in load could occur, resulting in flexural strengthening due to the fibres. On the other hand, no such discontinuity in the load vs. displacement plots was observed in the case of polypropylene fibres, where the matrix failure also resulted in the simultaneous breaking of the fibres across the crack; this produced little or no flexural strengthening due to the fibres. The marginally higher peak bending loads (Tables 1 and 2) observed in the case of polypropylene fibre reinforced concrete compared to plain concrete are probably due to the role played by the fibres as crack arresters controlling the growth of subcritical flaws.

Both the plain and fibre reinforced concretes were found to be strain rate sensitive. The general effect of increasing the strain rate was to increase the peak bending loads and the fracture energies. Fibres were found to increase the impact resistance significantly. Polypropylene fibres were found to increase the toughness by a factor of 2 to 4 in the static case, but only by a factor of less than 2 in the dynamic case. On the other hand, the addition of steel fibres increased the toughness by a factor of 10 to 20 in the static case; this was reduced to a factor of only 3 to 4 in the dynamic case. This may have been because of the increased incidence of steel fibres breaking in the case of impact loading compared to static loading.

As expected, plain high strength concrete beams were found to be more brittle than plain normal strength beams under both static and impact loading (Tables 1 and 2). The addition of fibres also reduced the brittleness of HS concrete (Table 2 and Figs. 5 and 6). On comparing the performance of polypropylene fibres to steel fibres in the HS matrix, it can be seen that the steel fibres are much more effective. Also, a comparison of steel fibre reinforced normal strength concrete with steel fibre reinforced high strength concrete (Tables 1 and 2) indicates that steel fibres are more efficient in HS concrete than in NS concrete. This may be due to improved fibre-matrix bond attained in high strength concrete (3) due to the presence of microsilica.

CONCLUSIONS

1. The use of fibres, both steel and polypropylene, was found to improve the ductility of a plain concrete matrix. High modulus steel fibres with hooked ends were more effective than the low modulus fibrillated polypropylene fibres.
2. Both plain and fibre reinforced concretes are strain rate sensitive. Their properties are significantly changed when the strain rates are increased from the static rates to those associated with impact. In general, an increase in the strain rate resulted in an increase in both strength and toughness. The fibre composites, especially those made with steel fibres, were found to be much more impact resistant than the plain unreinforced matrix.

3. The brittleness of high strength concrete can be decreased by using fibres. Steel fibres in particular were more efficient in the HS matrix than in the NS matrix, probably due to the improved fibre-matrix bond.

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